

TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE CONTACTS FOR TEMPERATURE SENSORS

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ANNOTATION: Another type of sensors is determined by the nature of its physical nature. The output amount, that is, resistance, inductance, capacitance, voltage, phase, phase, frequency sensors are the most common.

Keywords: Different types of sensors, the amount of output is determined depending on the physical nature. Sensors whose output is electrical, i.e. resistance, inductance, capacitance, current, voltage, phase, frequency sensors are the most common.

The formation of contacts is one of the final and most important operations in the technological process of manufacturing composite temperature sensors, because the active structure of this device has already been produced, and the characteristics of the device, as a whole, changes in its performance depend on the quality of the contacts [1].

The specific resistance of the contact is exponentially dependent on the ratio of the height of the contact potential barrier to the root of the doping concentration of the area where the contact is formed. When $N > 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, the specific resistance (R_c) of the contact is mainly determined by the tunneling processes and decreases rapidly with the increase of the alloying level. Therefore, high doping or low barrier height F_v is required to obtain small R_c . In the production of ohmic contacts, it is

also necessary to take into account that the height of the energy barrier F_v is very sensitive to the heat treatment before and after the deposition of the sample [2].

Conventional contacts used in the manufacture of temperature sensors are not suitable for our conditions, because they are Au, Ag, Pd, Pt. based on precious metals. Research on the creation of contacts was carried out on the basis of metals Ni, Al, Cu, Cr, Ti [3].

In general, the main task of the metallization stage in the development of temperature sensor manufacturing technology was to create ohmic contacts with an active structure [4].

Spraying based on thermovacuum process 10^{-6} Torr was carried out at residual pressure, which was achieved by sequentially driving air from the chamber with vacuum and diffusion pumps. The heating of the substance was carried out by direct transmission of electric current through a refractory crucible [5].

The quality of the resulting film is strongly dependent on the grain size and the temperature during the sputtering of the substrate, and is determined by its adhesion to the silicon surface. Also, under equal conditions, a fine-grained structure is formed from metals W, Mo, Ta, Pt, Ni with a high vaporization temperature [6]. Coarse-grained films are formed by metals with a low evaporation temperature, for example: Zn, Cd, Al. It should be taken into account that when the thickness of the film exceeds $2\ \mu\text{m}$, due to the elastic tension created between the substrate and the film, the adhesion decreases and even complete delamination of the film is possible.

Good adhesion is achieved by sputtering chemically related metals to the base material. So, for silicon, chemisorption occurs during the deposition of easily oxidizable metals Al, Cr, Mn, Ti, W. Gold, silver, palladium have a low adhesion to silicon [7].

The process of thermal vacuum deposition was carried out on VUP-4, VUP-5 and UVN-75 devices. The VUP-4 and VUP-5 laboratory devices made it possible to deposit metal films by heating refractory boats and spirals by passing electric current through them. UVN-75 is a mechanized vacuum device for depositing electron

beams of films, designed for vacuum deposition of thin films of metal, semiconductor materials and dielectrics by electron beam evaporation. The setup allows simultaneous deposition of the same metal, semiconductor, and dielectric films on the substrate surface in the desired sequence, controlling the substrate temperature and film thickness [8]. Refractory spirals, crucibles and boats are made of tungsten, tantalum or molybdenum. In order to obtain high-quality metal films with good adhesion, metal sputtering was carried out on silicon at a substrate temperature of 200-400 °C.

Research on the formation of contacts (conducted on the basis of metals Ni, Al, Cu, Cr, Ti, as mentioned above) gave the following results. The structure of contacts is as follows, Al-Ti-Ni for p-type, Ti-Ni for n-type. X is correct. Single-layer nickel contacts have proven themselves well [9].

Ti's ability to form a strong bond with SiO₂ allows it to be recommended for adhesive bonding with crystals. Titanium deposited on Si surface adheres well and interacts with silicon dioxide: $Ti + SiO_2 = TiO_2 + Si$. The resulting titanium dioxide has good conductivity compared to SiO₂, as a result of which we have silicon with a low contact resistance of $2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Ohm} \cdot \text{cm}$ and an alloying concentration of 10^{20} cm^{-3} . Due to the rapid oxidation of Ti in air and the property of tinning in a vacuum chamber, a layer of Ni is sprayed on Ti, which protects Ti from oxidation. During cleaning, the vacuum in the chamber should not be less than 10^{-6} torr. The surface of the pallets is thoroughly cleaned before laying the film [10].

It is recommended to spray the contacts through the stencil. Templates are independently made of metal foils with a thickness of 100-200 μm.

Chemical deposition of nickel was also investigated to create ohmic contacts. To improve nickel adhesion, the plates were polished in M-9 micropowder before nickel plating and treated in a hydrofluoric acid solution (HF:H₂O 1:1 ratio) to remove the oxide. Electrolyte for nickel plating is prepared according to the following recipe for 100 ml of solution [11]:

nickel chloride (NiCl₂) -2,1 g

sodium hypophosphite (NaH_2PO_2) -2,4 г

triple substituted sodium citrate -4,5 г

ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl) -3 г

aqueous ammonia (25%) - 5g

The process of nickel plating was carried out in the following order, electrolyte was poured into nickel-plated vessels (without ammonia and sodium hypophosphite) and heated to 86-90 C on a hot plate, then ammonia sodium hypophosphite was added to the solution and silicon wafers were lowered. Nickel plating time 40 ± 20 s. Electrolyte temperature was monitored with a mercury thermometer. After nickel plating, the nickel surface should have a light yellow color and be uniformly coated with nickel; nickel peeling or blistering is not possible [12].

To increase the adhesion of nickel, after nickel plating, the plates are heated in a vacuum at a temperature of 600 C for 30 minutes. The surface resistance of nickel was 8-15 ohms [13]. The adhesion of the nickel coating was determined by lightly scratching with a steel needle, if the coating is good, the nickel should not be peeled off or break the plate, then the nickel should not be broken with the plate and not be peeled off [14]. The ohmic resistance of the nickel coating was determined by measuring the current-voltage characteristics of the plates (VAX method) [15]. These boards were considered high-quality, they did not show rectification in the entire range of VAX operating voltage (0.1 - 5 V) [16].

References:

1. Эгамбердиев Б.Э., Садий Ш.Х. А. и Исраилов Ф.М. (2021). ЭЛЕКТРОННО-СПЕКТРОСКОПИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ЭПИТАКСИАЛЬНЫХ ПЛЕНОК CoSi_2 НА КРЕМНИИ. Журнал Физико-математические науки, 2(1).
2. Муродкосимович И. Ф., Ганишерович Б. А. и Суннатиевич А. Б. (2021). СПОСОБ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СТАНДАРТНОЙ ПОГРЕШНОСТИ ИЗМЕРЕНИЙ. Международный инженерный журнал исследований и разработок, 6 (ICDSIIL), 5-5.

3. Эгамбердиев Б., Исраилов Ф. и Рахматуллаев К. (2020). ДАТЧИКИ ВЛАЖНОСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМИКПОЗИЦИОННОГО МАТЕРИАЛА С НАНОРАЗМЕРНЫМИ СТРУКТУРАМИ. Евразийский журнал полупроводниковой науки и техники, 2(3), 36.
4. Исроилов Ф. М. Датчики влажности на основе композиционного материала с наноразмерными структурами //international scientific conference" innovative trends in science, practice and education". – 2023. – т. 2. – №. 2. – с. 81-88.
5. O'g B. O. N. et al. The role of quality management system in increasing product quality in enterprises //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 228-233.
6. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бердимуродов Г. Т., Бадалов У. Н. СИФАТЛИ МАХСУЛОТ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИЛИШИДА СИНОВ ВА ЎЛЧОВЛАРНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //ЎТМОИЙ ФАНЛАРДА ИННОВАСИЯ ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 101-106.
7. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МАҲСУЛОТЛАР СИФАТИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ //Academic research in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 38-45.
8. Juraboyevich B. N. et al. Development Of Metrology And The Role And Importance Of Metrological Supply In Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 136-139.
9. Juraboyevich B. N., Son B. O. N. THE ROLE OF QUALITY PRODUCTION IN ENTERPRISES //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 9. – №. 10. – С. 644-647.
10. BADALOV U. N. O. THE IMPORTANCE OF TESTING LABORATORIES AND THEIR ACCREDITATION //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 163-169.

11. Juraboevich B. N. Products in Manufacturing Enterprises the Essence of Quality Management //International Journal of Development and Public Policy. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 117-118.
12. Jo‘raboevich B. N. QUALITY EXPORT PRODUCTS IN ENTERPRISES GENERAL AND SPECIAL IN PRODUCTION IMPORTANCE OF REGULATIONS //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 1-7.
13. Jo‘raboyevich B. N. ROLE OF COMPARISON, CALIBRATION AND METROLOGICAL CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 168-175.
14. BADALOV N. J., RUSTAMOV N. T. THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES THAT HAVE IMPLEMENTED A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 46-55.
15. Badalov N. J. MANAGE PRODUCT QUALITY IN ENTERPRISES CONTENT //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 58-64.
16. Jo‘raboevich B. N., Abduraxmonovich S. H. M. KORXONALARDA O ‘LCHASH VOSITALARNI SINOVDAN O ‘TKAZISHDA METROLOGIK XIZMATINING O ‘RNI //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 701-704.